

Quantitative Evaluation of Zhejiang Rural Industrial Integration Policy Based on the PMC Index Model

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Abstract:

Rural industrial integration is conducive to accelerating the development of rural agriculture, which provides powerful impetus for rural revitalization. This paper mainly uses mixed research method and selects Zhejiang Province as the research object. By sorting out, quantifying and analyzing the rural industrial integration policies of Zhejiang Province based on the PMC index model, the relevant policies are evaluated. The results show that the overall design of Zhejiang Province's rural industrial integration policies is generally reasonable; the policies are goal-oriented, fact-based and well-planned. However, there are still some problems need to be improved on. And it is necessary to improve the nature of policies, optimize the functions and appropriately extend the timeliness of the rural industrial integration policy in the future.

Keywords: rural industrial integration policy; PMC index model; Zhejiang Province

1. Introduction

At present, China has built a well-off society in an all-round way and has entered a new stage of building a modern socialist country. The issues relating to agriculture, rural areas and farmers are the key concern of China's economic development and the fundamental issue concerning the people's livelihood. "To increase farmers' income, we must promote the integrated development of the primary, secondary, and tertiary industries in rural areas" was first proposed in the Number one Central Document in 2015. Since then, governments at all levels and academia have paid more attention to rural industrial integration. In 2017, the rural revitalization strategy was first proposed. And the implementation of rural revitalization has become the overall strategy of our party and the country to solve the "three rural" issues. Realizing the thriving businesses of rural areas takes the first place in the overall requirements of this strategy, which highlights the important role of rural industry development. Only by constantly improving the level of industrial development can we provide a good material foundation for rural revitalization. The rural industrial integration accords with the development trend of modern agriculture. The essence of rural industrial integration is to develop rural secondary and tertiary industries based on agriculture, to carry out intensive cross-industry integration with limited elements and technical capacity, to break the inherent constraints and single state of agricultural products processing, production and sales, and to make the primary, secondary and tertiary industries closely combined, so as to finally increase farmers' income, form a good industrial state, develop rural economy and promote rural revitalization.

As the demonstration zone for common prosperity in China, Zhejiang Province has proposed to promote the rural industrial integration since 2011 and has been in the forefront in China now. In recent years, Zhejiang Province has made great efforts to promote the development of rural industrial integration and achieved certain results. Since the construction work of national demonstration parks for rural industrial integration was launched in 2017, Zhejiang has created 10 national demonstration parks, while carrying out the construction of provincial demonstration parks. At present, a total of 34 demonstration parks on rural industrial integration are under construction in the province, showing the potential of flourishing development. Therefore, the selection of Zhejiang Province as the research object for policy evaluation is conducive to understanding the typical characteristic and effects of China's rural industrial integration policies, and can provide reference for industrial integration policies in other parts of the country.

To sum up, it is of great theoretical and practical significance to study the rural industrial integration policy of Zhejiang Province. And the purpose of this paper is mainly to evaluate the rural industrial integration policies of Zhejiang Province based on the PMC index model, in order to provide decision-making reference and theoretical guidance and promote the stable and rapid development of rural industrial integration. Content analysis method is mainly adopted to analyze the nature, subject, field, function and so on of the relevant policies, and on this basis, the policy evaluation index system is constructed, and the index

value is measured by quantitative method and the policies are quantitatively evaluated. And some policy suggestions will finally put forward after the analysis of the policy evaluation results. To some extent, the combination of quantitative and qualitative methods may make this research more comprehensive, scientific and reasonable.

2. Literature review

Rosenberg, an American scholar, first proposed (1963) the concept of technological convergence. He argued that the emergence of the machine industry is due to the application of the same technology in different industries, which can be called technological convergence¹. And the academic research on rural industrial integration mainly focuses on the connotation, motivation, mode and effect of rural industrial integration. Changyun Jiang (2015) argued that the integration of rural primary, secondary and tertiary industries fundamentally belongs to industrial integration. It drives the integration, optimization and reorganization of resources, factors, technologies and market demands in rural areas and even the adjustment of rural industrial spatial distribution by forming new technologies, new types of business and new business models². An Xie & Ying Zhou (2017) argued that rural industrial integration is the strategic adjustment made in response to the change of relative endowments of agricultural economic resources in China. Rural industrial integration is based on technology innovation, which increases the labor input per unit, makes up for the internal division of labor of land scale by service scale, and breaks through the market constraints by the diversity of agricultural supply and marketing innovation³. Zhong Yuan (2022) explored the correlation between rural industrial integration and rural revitalization strategy, pointed out that we need to implement systematic and long-term plans, fully mobilize the initiative of agriculture, rural areas and farmers, and make concerted efforts through multi-party coordination, multiple policies, multiple mechanisms, and multiple types of resources, so as to realize the correlated development of rural industrial integration and rural revitalization strategy⁴. Aihua Xiong & Han Zhang (2019), from the perspective of agricultural business entities, pointed out that there are three modes of rural industrial integration: agricultural business entities extend forward and backward along the industrial chain; agricultural business entities expand new functions of agriculture; new types of agricultural business entities popularize and apply advanced technology⁵. Turiyanskiy, A. V., et al. (2019) found that rural industrial integration is an important reserve of rural socio-economic development. It is consistent with the idea of rural development and promotes the evolutionary formation and placement of rural productivity⁶. Kim, K. C., Mun, E., Lee, S. S., Koo, S. M., Lee, D. K., & Son, Y. H. (2017) analyzed the development situation, policy objectives and actual condition of the rural industrial integration district, pointed out the existing problems and puts forward the corresponding improvement plans in order to lead the early settlement and management for policy objectives⁷. Das, V. K. & Ganesh-Kumar, A. (2018) examined the role of diversification in rural industrial integration on farmers' income. They found that the diversification of agricultural production and the size of the farm will maximize the income of farmers⁸.

In summary, the academic research on rural industrial integration mainly focuses on the development of rural industrial integration from the macro aspect, and there are few studies focusing on the micro level, such as a specific province. And there is relatively little research on the evaluation of rural industrial integration policy. Therefore, this paper takes the research gap of literature as the starting point to deeply study the rural industrial integration policy at the micro level, hoping to fill the research gap from the perspective of practice in some way.

3. Theoretical basis

This research is based on policy evaluation theory and the PMC index model. The first is the policy evaluation theory. The core issue in the whole process of policy evaluation is to determine the policy evaluation standard and establish the evaluation index system. Zhenming Chen, a famous public administration scholar in China, constructs the policy evaluation standard, which is divided into three categories: policy system, policy process and policy results. The evaluation standard of policy system includes the evaluation standard of policy subject, policy object, policy environment and policy instrument, such as legitimacy, rationality, appropriateness, effectiveness, responsiveness, suitability, adequacy and overall indicators of social development, etc. The evaluation standard of policy process includes the evaluation standard of policy formulation, implementation, monitoring, evaluation and termination process,

such as executive capacity, responsiveness, adequacy, appropriateness, public participation, predictability, procedural fairness, feasibility, policy impact, social sustainable development, etc. The evaluation standard of policy results includes efficiency, effectiveness, workload, responsiveness, adequacy, fairness, appropriateness, performance, productivity, etc. He argues that we should choose the evaluation standard and make it legal and reasonable according to the actual situation and the evaluation contents because the policy evaluation standard varies with evaluation objectives, methods and emphases⁹. And this paper will be based on Professor Zhenming Chen's policy evaluation standard, which is conducive to better quantitative evaluation of the policies.

And the second is PMC index model. PMC stands for Policy Modeling Consistency Index. It is proposed by Ruiz Estrada in 2011. He believes that all things in the world are in a system of continuous movement and there is a connection. Therefore, the influence of various factors on policies should be considered when establishing a policy research model, and no variable should be ignored. PMC-Index involves four basic steps: first, the use of multi-input-output table; second, classification of variables and identification of parameters; third, measurement of the PMC-Index; fourth, construction of the PMC-Surface. Ruiz Estrada divides the variables into ten main-variables, including (X1) types of research; (X2) research orientation; (X3) data sources; (X4) econometrics methods applied; (X5) areas of research; (X6) research theoretical framework; (X7) policy modeling by sectors; (X8) economics frameworks; (X9) geographical analysis; (X10) paper citation. He then divides the ten main-variables into fifty sub-variables. The final score of each main-variable is the mean of all sub-variables, and the PMC-Index is equal to the sum of the scores of all main-variables. According to the PMC-Index, the evaluation results can be divided into excellent, good, acceptable, and poor performance, so as to obtain the evaluation grade of the policy¹⁰.

4. Analysis

(1) Data source and collection

In this study, keyword "rural industrial integration" was searched on relevant websites of government departments and Chinalawinfo Database. In order to ensure the representativeness and accuracy of policy selection, the following selection principles are established. Firstly, relevance. The selected policy texts are highly relevant to rural industrial integration and have high validity. Secondly, authority. The document-issuing agency of the selected policies are the relevant government departments in Zhejiang Province. Thirdly, openness. The selected policy texts are publicly released on authoritative platforms and with high reliability. After sorting out, a total of 40 valid policies that include "rural industrial integration" in the texts have been collected since 2016.

(2) Classification of variables and identification of parameters

This paper draws lessons from the variable determination method proposed by Ruiz Estrada, the policy evaluation standard proposed by Professor Zhenming Chen and the policy evaluation index system established by Yong'an Zhang et al¹¹. Based on the modification of policy evaluation index in existing references and the actual development status and characteristics of Zhejiang rural industrial integration policies, a total of 9 main-variables and 30 sub-variables are set. (as shown in Table 1).

After constructing the quantitative evaluation framework based on the PMC index model, this research selects 8 comprehensive, highly correlated and representative rural industrial integration policies from the 40 policies searched by relevant websites of government departments, Chinalawinfo Database and other channels as samples to conduct empirical research, covering 4 provincial policies and 4 prefecture-level policies. The wide range of samples is conducive to guaranteeing the accuracy and reference of research results. And these 8 sample policies are marked as P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, and P8 respectively. The 8 sample policies are summarized as follows (as shown in Table 2).

Table 1 Evaluation index system of rural industrial integration policy

Main-variable	Sub-variable	Evaluation standard of sub-variable
X1 nature of the policy	(X _{1,1}) predicting	judge whether the policy is predictive
	(X _{1,2}) supervising	judge whether the policy involves supervision
	(X _{1,3}) supporting	judge whether the policy is supportive
	(X _{1,4}) guiding	judge whether the policy is guiding
X2 policy limitation	(X _{2,1}) long-term	judge whether the policy limitation is longer than 10 years
	(X _{2,2}) medium-term	judge whether the policy limitation is within 6-10 years
	(X _{2,3}) short-term	judge whether the policy limitation is within 1-5 years
X3 policy object	(X _{3,1}) industries	judge whether the policy involves industries
	(X _{3,2}) enterprises	judge whether the policy involves enterprises
	(X _{3,3}) industrial parks	judge whether the policy involves industrial parks
	(X _{3,4}) farmers	judge whether the policy involves farmers
X4 policy domain	(X _{4,1}) economy	judge whether the policy has economic implications
	(X _{4,2}) politics	judge whether the policy has political implications
	(X _{4,3}) society	judge whether the policy has social implications
	(X _{4,4}) technology	judge whether the policy involves new technologies
	(X _{4,5}) environment	judge whether the policy has environmental implications
X5 policy function	(X _{5,1}) institutional constraint	judge whether the policy involves institutional constraints
	(X _{5,2}) specification and guidance	judge whether the policy involves specification and guidance
	(X _{5,3}) technological innovation	judge whether the policy involves technological innovation
X6 incentive measures	(X _{6,1}) financial support	judge whether the policy involves providing financial support
	(X _{6,2}) tax subsidy	judge whether the policy involves providing tax subsidy
	(X _{6,3}) talent motivation	judge whether the policy involves providing talent motivation
	(X _{6,4}) advantageous resources	judge whether the policy involves providing advantageous resources
X7 policy evaluation	(X _{7,1}) goal-oriented	judge whether the policy is goal-oriented
	(X _{7,2}) fact-based	judge whether the policy is fact-based
	(X _{7,3}) well-planned	judge whether the policy is well-planned, executable
X8 policy perspective	(X _{8,1}) macro view	judge whether the policy perspective is macro
	(X _{8,2}) medium view	judge whether the policy perspective is medium
	(X _{8,3}) micro view	judge whether the policy perspective is micro
X9 whether the public	-	judge whether the policy is open

Table 2 Summary of sample policies

Serial Number	Policy Name	Issuing Time
P1	Several Opinions of The People’s Government of Zhejiang Province on Promoting High Quality Development of Rural Industry	2020.08.14
P2	Implementation Opinions of General Office of The People’s Government of Zhejiang Province on Accelerating the Rural Integrated Development of Primary, Secondary and Tertiary Industries	2016.12.05
P3	Circular of Zhejiang Provincial Development and Reform Commission and Other 7 Departments on Printing and Distributing the List of The Third Batch of Provincial-Level Demonstration Parks for Rural Industrial Integration	2021.07.19
P4	Circular of Zhejiang Provincial Development and Reform Commission on Printing and Distributing 2021 Key Project Investment Plan for Zhejiang Provincial Rural Revitalization Landmark Project	2021.06.30
P5	Implementation Opinions of People’s Government of Zhoushan Municipality on Promoting Industrial Integration and High-Quality Development of Rural Industry	2022.03.07
P6	Circular of Ningbo Agricultural Industrialization Leading Group Office on Constructing the Strong Town of National Agricultural Industry	2021.01.28
P7	Circular of Huzhou People’s Government Office on Guaranteeing the Construction of “Standard Land” Project for Rural Industrial Integration to Promote the Rural Industry Revitalization	2019.06.28
P8	Opinions of Jiaxing People’s Government Office on Accelerating The Integrated Development of Rural Industries	2019.05.17

(3) Construction of the multi-input-output table

Then set the value of all sub-variables to zero or one for the multiple input-output table. The scoring method is to observe whether the contents of policy texts correspond to the content of sub-variables in the

table. If the policy text conforms to the sub-variable, the value of the sub-variable corresponding to this policy is 1; otherwise, the value is 0. The values of all sub-variables obey the binomial distribution. $X \sim N [0,1]$; $X = \{XR: [0\sim 1]\}$.

The multi-input-output table can measure any single variable in multiple dimensions, so that the advantages and disadvantages of rural industrial integration policies can be analyzed from every dimension, which is conducive to providing a basis for quantitative analysis. The multi-input-output table consists of all main-variables and sub-variables. Main-variables are independent of each other, and each main-variable is subdivided into several sub-variables with equal weight. Based on the characteristics of Zhejiang Province’s rural industrial integration policy and the variable settings as above, the multi-input-output table is constructed (as shown in Table 3).

Table 3 Multi-input-output table

P	X1				X2			X3				X4				
	X _{1:1}	X _{1:2}	X _{1:3}	X _{1:4}	X _{2:1}	X _{2:2}	X _{2:3}	X _{3:1}	X _{3:2}	X _{3:3}	X _{3:4}	X _{4:1}	X _{4:2}	X _{4:3}	X _{4:4}	X _{4:5}
P1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
P2	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
P3	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
P4	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
P5	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1
P6	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
P7	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
P8	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
P	X5			X6				X7			X8		X9			
	X _{5:1}	X _{5:2}	X _{5:3}	X _{6:1}	X _{6:2}	X _{6:3}	X _{6:4}	X _{7:1}	X _{7:2}	X _{7:3}	X _{8:1}	X _{8:2}	X _{8:3}	X _{9:1}	-	-
P1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	-	-
P2	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	-	-
P3	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	-	-
P4	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	-	-
P5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	-	-
P6	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	-	-
P7	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	-	-
P8	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	-	-

(4) Measurement of the PMC-Index

The advantage of PMC-Index is that the variable setting is based on comprehensive analysis and mining of policy texts, which can avoid subjectivity and improve the accuracy of the evaluation. The value of main-variables, sub-variables and PMC-Index (as shown in Table 4) are calculated according to the formula as below.

$X \sim N [0,1], X = \{XR: [0\sim 1]\}$

$$X_{t=} = \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{X_{tj}}{n} \quad t = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6,7,8,9$$

$$PMC = \sum_{t=1}^m X_t \quad m=9$$

Table 4 Summary of PMC-Index of eight rural industrial integration polices

	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	Mean Value
X1	1	1	0.75	0.5	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.781
X2	0.333	0.333	0.333	0.333	0.333	0.333	0.333	0.333	0.333
X3	1	0.75	0.75	1	0.75	0.25	0.5	1	0.75
X4	0.8	0.8	0.2	0.8	0.6	0.2	0.4	0.8	0.575
X5	1	1	0.333	0.333	1	0.667	0.667	1	0.75
X6	1	0.75	0.5	0.75	1	0.25	0.5	1	0.719
X7	1	1	0.667	1	1	0.667	1	1	0.917
X8	0.333	0.333	0.333	0.333	0.333	0.333	0.333	0.333	0.333
X9	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PMC-Index	7.466	6.966	4.866	6.049	6.766	4.45	5.483	7.216	6.158
Level	good	good	acceptable	good	good	acceptable	acceptable	good	-
Ranking	1	3	7	5	4	8	6	2	-

(5) Construction of the PMC-Surface

In order to more clearly and intuitively show the calculation results of the PMC index model running in the sample policies and the advantages and disadvantages of the evaluated policy from all dimensions, the PMC-Surface is drawn based on the PMC-Index obtained above. Since there are 9 main-variables, a 3 * 3 PMC-Matrix can be constructed, and the third-order matrix can be used to construct the PMC-Surface. The computational formula of PMC-Surface is shown below.

$$PMC\text{-Surface} = \begin{pmatrix} X1 & X2 & X3 \\ X4 & X5 & X6 \\ X7 & X8 & X9 \end{pmatrix}$$

And Figure 1-Figure 8 show the PMC-Surface of each evaluated policy respectively.

Figure 1 PMC-Surface of P1

Figure 2 PMC-Surface of P2

Figure 3 PMC-Surface of P3

Figure 4 PMC-Surface of P4

Figure 5 PMC-Surface of P5

Figure 6 PMC-Surface of P6

Figure 7 PMC-Surface of P7

Figure 8 PMC-Surface of P8

(6) Analysis of empirical results

This research refers to Ruiz Estrada's policy evaluation standard and divides the PMC-Index into four levels: excellent performance (8-9), good performance (6-7. 99), acceptable performance (4-5. 99), poor performance (0-3. 99)¹⁰.

From a macro point of view, among these evaluated policies, P1, P8, P2, P5, P4, P7, P3 and P6 are ranked from highest to lowest by PMC-Index. According to the policy evaluation standard, the level of policy P1, P2, P4, P5 and P8 is good, while the level of policy P3, P6 and P7 is acceptable. The mean value of the PMC-Index of the eight policies is 6.158, which is at the good level, indicating that the rural industrial integration policies of Zhejiang Province are generally reasonable. That also indicates that governments at all levels in Zhejiang Province actively implement the national strategy when formulating the rural industrial integration policies, consider comprehensively and conform to local realities, but there is still room for further improvement.

From the perspective of the main-variables, the mean value of X9, X7 and X1 are relatively large, while the mean value of X4 is small, which shows that rural industrial integration policies of Zhejiang Province have clear target, are based on abundant evidence and well-planned. The governments do well in policy disclosure. The nature and function of these policies are relatively comprehensive, but the policy domain still needs further optimization and improvement. The mean value of policy limitation (X2) is 0.333, reflecting that the target date of Zhejiang Province's rural industrial integration policy is relatively single, and there is a serious lack of mid - and long-term policies. And the mean value of policy perspective (X8) is also 0.333, reflecting that the policy perspective is also relatively single, with more macro perspective and less micro and medium perspective. In terms of policy objects (X3), the existing policies for rural industrial integration in Zhejiang Province are mostly focused on industries and enterprises, while there are few micro policies for farmers or industrial parks that play an important role in rural industrial integration.

5. Discussion

The PMC-Index of rural industrial integration policy P1 is 7.466, ranking first with a "good" grade, which is significantly higher than the mean value of the PMC-Index. The values of the main-variables of this policy are equal to or higher than the average level, indicating that the government of Zhejiang Province comprehensively considered and involved all dimensions of the rural industrial integration policy when formulating the policy P1. The policy planning is clear and reasonable, and the measures are in place. The weakness is the timeliness and perspective of the policy, and more attention should be paid to the mid - and long-term and medium and micro perspectives.

The PMC-Index of rural industrial integration policy P2 is 6.966, ranking third with a "good" grade, which is higher than the mean value of the PMC-Index. The values of the main-variables of this policy are equal to or higher than the average level. However, there is still room for improvement in policy object (X3)

and incentive measures (X6), and these two aspects can be given priority in policy improvement according to the actual situation.

The PMC-Index of rural industrial integration policy P3 is 4.866, ranking seventh with an “acceptable” grade, which is significantly lower than the mean value of the PMC-Index. The problems are mainly in the five aspects: nature of the policy (X1), policy domain (X4), policy function (X5), incentive measures(X6) and policy evaluation(X7), and the values of these five aspects are all lower than the average. For policy improvement, the government can first consider improving policy function (X5), and then consider improving X4, X6, X7 and X1, namely the improvement sequence for reference is: X5-X4-X6-X7-X1.

The PMC-Index of rural industrial integration policy P4 is 6.049, ranking fifth with a “good” grade. Among the main-variables of this policy, except that nature of the policy (X1) and policy function (X5) are slightly lower than the average level, other indicators are higher than or equal to the average level, indicating that the government has taken comprehensive consideration in formulating policy P4. However, this policy can still be improved from the aspects of policy nature and function, and the improvement sequence for reference is X5-X1.

The PMC-Index of rural industrial integration policy P5 is 6.766, ranking fourth with a “good” grade. Among the main-variables of this policy, except that nature of the policy (X1) is lower than the average level, other indicators are higher than or equal to the average level. However, the policy domain (X4) is slightly above the average and still needs further improvement. Therefore, the improvement sequence of this policy for reference is: X1-X4.

The PMC-Index of rural industrial integration policy P6 is 4.45, ranking last and is much lower than the average PMC-Index (6.158). Among the main-variables of this policy, nature of the policy (X1), policy object (X3), policy domain (X4), policy function (X5), incentive measures(X6) and policy evaluation(X7) are lower than the average level, so this policy should be improved from these six aspects. And the improvement sequence of this policy for reference is X6-X4-X3-X7-X5-X1.

The PMC-Index of rural industrial integration policy P7 is 5.483, ranking sixth with an “acceptable” grade. Among the main-variables of this policy, nature of the policy (X1), policy object (X3), policy domain (X4), policy function (X5), and incentive measures(X6) are lower than the average level, so this policy should be improved from these five aspects. And the improvement sequence of this policy for reference is X3-X6-X4-X5-X1.

The PMC-Index of rural industrial integration policy P8 is 7.216, ranking second with a “good” grade. Among the main-variables of this policy, except that nature of the policy (X1) is lower than the average level, other indicators are higher than or equal to the average level. Therefore, the policy P8 should be further improved from the aspect of the nature of the policy(X1). From the perspective of sub-variables, P8 should involve some predictive policy contents, which is conducive to the improvement of this policy.

6. Conclusions

(1) Summary

Through the quantitative evaluation of Zhejiang Province’s rural industrial integration policies by the PMC index model, this paper finds that the overall design of Zhejiang Province’s rural industrial integration policies is generally reasonable, the policies are goal-oriented, fact-based and well-planned. The eight evaluated policies are all at or above the acceptable level, and five of them are rated as “good”. These policies have promoted the rural industrial integration in Zhejiang Province to a certain extent. However, there are still some problems, such as the lack of predictive policies, incomplete policy domains, policy functions that have not been effectively played, inadequate incentive measures, incomplete coverage of policy functions, etc.

(2) Policy suggestions

First, improve the nature of policies and enhance the predictability and operability of rural industrial integration policies. In the future design and formulation of rural industrial integration policies, the government should not neglect the predictability of policy while paying attention to the nature of policy supervision, support and guidance. Introducing the prediction mechanism of rural industrial integration policy is conducive to focusing on the long term, thus promoting the policy optimization.

Second, optimize the functions of Zhejiang Province's rural industrial integration policy. The current rural industrial integration policy of Zhejiang Province lacks the function of technological innovation, so the policy function should be further optimized. The government should focus on encouraging innovation and giving more support to technological innovation when formulating policies. Through the extension of industrial chain and the transformation of development mode, new technology and new business model can be formed to drive the integration, optimization and reorganization of resources, elements, technologies and market demand in rural areas.

Third, appropriately extend the timeliness of the rural industrial integration policy. Zhejiang Province's existing rural industrial integration policies are mostly short-term policies, the follow-up policy formulation should not only focus on the short-term, but should appropriately add medium-term or long-term related policies, focusing on the medium-term and long-term planning of rural industrial integration.

(3) Limitations

First, constrained by the availability of data, there may be omissions in the collection of Zhejiang Province's rural industrial integration policies. Second, the setting of policy evaluation index in this paper mainly refers to the index setting in existing studies. There may be some omissions in terms of the combination with the actual situation of Zhejiang Province, resulting in the problem in the standardization of index system construction, which needs to be paid more attention in the future research. For the subsequent research, the variable setting can be further improved so as to enhance the universality of variable selection, and further optimize the application of PMC index model in the research.

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